

VALUE-BASED AND PRAGMATIC FEATURES OF ENGLISH PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS RELATED TO LABOR AND PROFESSIONAL ACTIVITY

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ABSTRACT

This article is devoted to the analysis of the linguocultural characteristics of phraseological units related to labor and professional activity, including their value-based and pragmatic aspects. Through the analysis of idioms related to professional activity and laboratory in the English language, society's attitude to labor, responsibility, and success is studied, and their role in interpersonal communication, as well as their benefits, is explained. The analysis once again confirms that linguistic units are an important link between culture and language.

Introduction. Language is the most important and easiest way to learn about the world, and in addition, it reflects the unique traditions, characteristics, and worldview of each society, today the study and teaching of foreign languages is considered a vital priority issue. Special attention should be paid to the phraseological units of the language being studied, which embody the above-mentioned features and characteristics. Phraseological units are a window into national culture, embodying values, traditions, and social concepts, as well as concepts related to professional activity and labor [1]. Since phraseological units related to labor and activity reflect the attitude of society to labor, professional ethics, and labor culture, their study from a linguocultural perspective is one of the scientific areas of modern linguistics that has gained particular importance.

Despite the fact that the linguocultural characteristics of professional phraseological units have been widely studied by linguists for several years, this topic has not lost its relevance. Because through these units we can study and analyze the attitude of a particular society to labor and work. The purpose of this article is to analyze the most important linguocultural characteristics of English phraseological units related to labor and professional activity using several examples.

Main body.

The main types of linguistic and cultural features:

1. Value-based linguocultural features

2. Pragmatic linguocultural features

Value-based linguocultural features

Linguistic sub-cultural features based on values show that linguistic units reflect the moral and social values of society. Linguistic units reflect the value system of a particular culture (Wierzbicka, 1997)[2]. For example,

The English idiom:

"bring home the bacon", it means to make a living, to provide for the family financially, that is, to earn money or to achieve success in some work.

"earn your bread and butter" means to make a living.

"make a living" is to earn the money one needs to pay for housing, food, etc.

"make ends meet" means to have enough money to buy what you need to live.

"reap the rewards" means to achieve a positive result through hard work or investment.

"reap the benefits", "enjoy the fruits of your labor", and "cash in on" are synonyms for the above idiom. These phraseological units mean that a person earns money and achieves success through work. From the point of view of linguocultural, such and similar units reflect the economic and social values of society.

Many idioms related to work express the values of hard work and dedication among peoples. The idea that idioms reflect the values and life experiences of a speech community was given by linguist David Crystal [3]. For example,

The expression "burn the midnight oil" means working late into the night.

"work your fingers to the bone" means working very hard.

"go to the extra mile" is used to describe going above and beyond what is expected.

"keep your nose to the grindstone" and "give it your all" are used to express working hard or working with all your might in professional activities. These idioms reflect the hard work of English society in achieving a goal or completing a task.

Phraseological units related to professional activity also express a person's professional success, experience and economic independence. For example:

"climb the career ladder" means a promotion to management with a higher salary

"build a career" means developing professional activity.

"make your mark" means making a name for yourself in a professional field.

"reach the top" means reaching a high position.

"hold down a job" means to keep a job for a long time.

These phraseological units promote the English to climb one step at a time in professional activity, to work on themselves.

As a result, the value-based linguocultural feature of phraseological units related to professional activity and labor reflects the values of society such as diligence, dedication, responsibility, and professional success. As a result of the study of such units, it can be seen that they clearly reflect the attitude and social views of society towards labor, as well as its cultural experience. Therefore, idioms are an important linguocultural tool that expresses the inextricable link between language and culture.

Pragmatic linguocultural features:

Pragmatic linguocultural features are related to the way phraseological units are used in the speech process. According to Teila, phraseological units perform a specific communicative function in the process of oral speech and are closely related to the cultural context [4]. According to George Yule, pragmatics studies the purpose for which language

units are used in real speech [5]. Some of the expressions are used in a formal business environment, while others are used in everyday speech. For example,

The expression "get down to business" means getting down to business or getting down to business and is often used in formal and semi-formal communication.

"snowed under with work" means buried in work.

"work around the clock", and "run oneself ragged" indicate that people spend most of their time on work. These units reflect the work pressure and professional responsibilities of modern English society in working life.

There are several phraseological units related to expressing one's opinion and taking responsibility in the process of teamwork, which are often used in the communicative process and serve to make communication short and effective. For example,

"think outside the box" means a creative and unconventional approach to problems, abandoning traditional patterns.

"be on the same page" means having the same idea.

"take the lead" means to take the initiative

"step up to the plate" means taking responsibility.

The pragmatic linguocultural features of phraseological units related to labor and professional activity are of particular importance in expressing real communication processes in a professional environment. Such units serve to briefly and concisely and figuratively express cooperation, decision-making, responsibility and other features in the process of activity. As a result, they are reflected as an important linguistic tool in making professional communication more effective, clear and understandable.

Conclusion. Linguocultural units are an important linguistic units that reflects the fundamental connection between language and culture. They express the traditions, values, worldview, and historical experience of each people through language. It is worth noting that phraseological units are considered one of the brightest manifestations of national culture, through which the mentality and social experience of each nation and people are manifested. Therefore, the study of linguocultural units is important not only for linguistics, but also for interethnic understanding.

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